

THE IMPACT OF TAX AND CUSTOMS PRIVILEGES ON THE PROSPERITY OF THE POPULATION

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Annotation: *This article summarizes the impact of VAT and import duty exemptions on the well-being of the population to ensure the population's demand for oil products. There are several reasons for the rise in vegetable oil prices. In foreign markets and exporting countries, production volumes are relatively low compared to previous seasons, in connection with which a regime of high customs duties on the export of sunflower oil and seeds has been introduced.*

Keywords: *value added tax, import customs duties, sunflower oil preferences, demand, real income, export.*

In order to fully meet the growing demand of the population for the main types of socially important food products in our country, to prevent rising prices and declining real incomes, some products are exempt from import duties and value added tax. Vegetable oil, sunflower and flax seeds, as well as soybeans, meat (beef, sheep, chicken), live animals (cattle and poultry) and products from their slaughter, potatoes and from frozen value added tax, bananas, plantain (fresh or dried) fresh or dried dates, figs, pineapples, avocados, guayava, mango and mangosteen or garcinia, fresh or dried citrus fruits, fresh papaya, fresh apples, products such as pears and quinces, kiwis were exempted from import customs duties.

But here's the question. Did the benefits work?

Vegetable and sunflower oil

Vegetable and sunflower oil products (excluding cottonseed oil), which are primary consumer products, will be exempt from value added tax from May 1, 2021. Imported vegetable oil was removed from the list of 529 types of goods banned from participation in public procurement. The average price of wire oil was 16,271 sums, an increase of 5,451 sums compared to the same period last year.

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compared to previous seasons, in connection with which a regime of high customs duties on the export of sunflower oil and seeds has been introduced.

The increase in import prices was due to the introduction of export restrictions by major partner countries. In particular, in Russia, the export duty on sunflower seeds outside the Eurasian Economic Union was increased from 6.5% to 30%, but not less than 165 euros per ton. served.

On the eve of the concession, large volumes of vegetable oil products were stored in customs warehouses without being sold by participants in foreign economic activity who intend to use them.

If we look at world market prices, we can see that the world market prices have also increased per ton of product. In December 2020, it was \$ 1.17 per 1 kg of sunflower oil, and in 2021 - In April, prices were sold at \$ 1.60. Due to the above preferences in our country, imports of oil products from some countries have increased. In the current year, imports of vegetable oil products amounted to 11 million US dollars, which is 61.9% less than in the same period last year.

Quantitatively, 25.8 thousand tons of vegetable oil were imported in January 2021, while 8.3 thousand tons of vegetable oil were imported this year. we can see the change.

If we rely on the laws of the market, the low supply relative to demand leads to higher prices. If one of the producers in the market produces a kilogram of vegetable oil for 10,000 sums and is ready to sell for 11,000 sums, if the importer also imported for 11,000 sums and is ready to sell for 12,000 sums, all sellers will sell at the same price if the equilibrium price is set at 13,000 sums.

Similarly, the lower the cost, whether producer or importer, is determined by supply and demand. If we analyze the average prices of vegetable oil consumed in the country, the average prices in June 2021 amounted to 20124 sums, while in January 2022 the prices amounted to 19431 sums. We can see that prices fell by 3.5% during the grace period. The effect of this VAT exemption may seem insignificant.

But if there were no taxes, prices would be more expensive and would lead to the welfare of the population, impoverishment. The exemption from value added tax served to keep prices from rising.

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